

A multi-referential method for research on several dimensions of a system

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A rule of thumb

Rule : more than one picture, diagram, etc. per page.

Example : a sky +Dali + a light house + a comb picture + a piece of mountain
+ a sun + a piece of cloud = Quixote and the windmill Page 10 + ten pictures of details

How to create, invent, a nice PhD dissertation ?

1998

I decide to write a PhD dissertation for myself.

This means that I already had worked on others' dissertations.

I had been a crutch for different authors in different disciplines.

Different kind of crutches : for the method, for the form, for the language - foreign students writing in French.

This work was both exiting and frustrating.

The frustration came from the fact that the authors were - or felt they were - obliged to follow « a set of rules ».

And, most of the time, this set of rules was unclear.

A long time ago

I begin to be a self-taught crutch for students preparing masters, etc.

I have to discover what should be a dissertation.

So I pay a visit to some research labs and I open the famous office cabinet with the label « dissertations ».

In many cases, what I read is « shaking » me.

The technical or terrain experience is interesting but the link with former models is unclear.

And the text patchwork is terrible.

I begin to develop - for « my » students - a « dimensions and referentials » method - D&R. This is based on my experience as a maintenance engineer.

In front of a symptom, the engineer has to select among the « dimensions » i.e. hardware and software modules which are the candidates for containing the failure.

He does so with his experience and knowledge - his referential - for the units and for the whole system.

1995

I discover the work of Jacques Ardoino and Coll. (5) and continue developing « the D&R method » with the help of these referential texts.

Dissertation after dissertation the method evolves up to become the D&R method for my PhD in 2005.

Since then, the method remained about the same.

Apple's pleasure for presentations

In 2007 I must buy an Apple computer for doing both movie making and music composition - in this case an Apple machine + softwares is cheaper than other scenarios.

I work with a set of software :

- GIMP - open source image editor - for preparing the pictures
- Sketchup Make to do the elements of the 3 D matrixes / cubes
- Keynote as a vector image editor to draw the final matrixes, etc.
- Pages text editor with vector image possibilities

It takes me years to improve my ability to realize nice and/or efficient diagrams.

The guy who described the Internet in 1981

« *Where do you come from ?* » is the question that arises.

I am a self-taught engineer in electronics and in computer science.

We must make some jumps forward and backward on the timeline.

1987

I discover artificial intelligence first trials and this leads me to study ... human intelligence, emotions, etc.

I am hired as a trainer for applied human sciences - I am also self-taught in these matters.
My boss tells me « *You should go to the university !* ».

A friend explains to me that there is a very special lab for self-taught people.

There, it is possible to make a research work to get a master's degree.

1998

I take as a research object what is now known as MOOCS - massive open online courses.

In 1998, the only MOOC I know is ... in my head.

The research lab I join is in the Information and communication sciences - a blend unique to France.

A little step backward.

1981

I am a kind of futurologist within the Alcatel company.

I describe the Internet as it will emerge 15 or 20 years further.

I have no crystal ball but :

- subscriptions to the main technical and scientific journals
- an account to Dialog information service for searching abstracts databases
- the ability for speed reading
- a sense for detecting small signals
- a sense for imagining how the pieces of the patchwork will merge

The red, blue, green, orange and violet cubes in the matrix represent different research projects that are not linked to each other.

I imagine that they will merge into a single « system » - grey, red & blue cube.

Indeed it merged and was named the Internet.

1998

I'm fed up to have no recognition of my work because I'm a self-taught person.

I discover another outstanding research lab, I3M - actually IMSIC on the French Riviera.
His boss - Philippe Dumas - is OK with the fact that « *Chris works in his kitchen* » as he says.

Why « *in his kitchen* » ?

Because I live 4 hundred kilometers from the lab.

Because my research object is « futuristic » and I have few local exchanges - some meetings in the year

Because I have exchanges with people in Europe and North America through the Internet and travelling. I present papers in U.K., Germany, Italy, Denmark, etc.

The invisible crossfade

The cross fade from « old » practices - in blue - to new tools - in red

In the 80's, the key tool for a seeker is ProQuest Dialog to get access to databases like PubMed/Medline - medicine, ERIC - education, INSPEC - computer, electronics, etc. In the 2010's most queries are made on Google.

It is impossible to say when did the turn happen from one scenario to the other.

Because this moment of the shift is unknown, it is difficult to know when the « new ideas » came in mind.

Thinking open knowledge garnerers

1990-95

I am fully devoted to my work in applied human sciences with few time for computers and networks.

1996

I work again on the link between computers, networks and content - and humans.

In 2005, I describe an « open knowledge garner » - PhD

WikiPedia started in 2001 with few influence on my research work.

The train of my system was already on its rails.

The start of the train

When did start my interest for « open » « commons », for « knowledge garner » for « online stuff » for « collective editing » ?

1986

The importance of commons is in my practice when I create what will become the Une fabrique de communs project.

I experiment collective edition when I help people write their dissertations.

OK, I think it is enough for presenting the author and his previous work.

A method for various dissertations

1995

Then I first use the term « multi-referential » - through the French term « multiréférentiel » used by Ardoino & Coll. (5)

The transformation of the understanding of a multi-referential method into diagrams was presented in my PhD in 2005.

The article Multiréférentialité was present in Wikipedia for more than 12 years. It is now « censored » but a copy can be found in SensAgent.

A few useful words

Seeker = knowledge seeker = academic researcher

Example of use of this word :

« Although we would like to believe that all undergraduate students are rigorous **seekers of knowledge**, the job that many college students are really trying to get done, from our observation, is to pass their courses without having to read the textbook at all. » Christinsen & Rainor

Usy, usies : a neologism for Heideggers' Zeug

In German, the « word » Zeug is mostly used in combinations : Rasierzeug, Sportzeug, Schulzeug.

The Wikipedia article « Heideggerian terminology » says « equipment » for Zeug.

The Heidegger's Zeug is for an XXX within its context.

Rasierzeug is pretty different from « shaving equipment ».

Sportzeug is pretty different from « sport equipment ».

Schulzeug is pretty different from « school equipment ».

In fact, any pre-existing word doesn't fit.

Either because of its meaning.

For example some translate Zeug with « stuff ».

Or by it's connotation - « equipment » sounds too modern for a manual grinding stone in the stone age !

Here are six examples of Zeug.

	Cracking, grinding	Move, displace
Zeug 1 Usy 1 A natural item	A manual grinding stone	A round log - Stone age
Zeug 2 Usy 2 A simple machine	A nutcracker (lever)	A wheelbarrow
Zeug 3 Usy 3 A machine with external force	A windmill	A solar charriot

Marissa Muller and her solar chariot : an usy

The fisherman, the basket maker and the weaver

7000 years ago

On the north of the Black sea and Caspian sea the first artisans in the Yamna culture create the indo-european language.

When an artisan creates a word, the word is both associated to the usy and to the corresponding gesture.

Fred, the fisherman, takes horse hair, turns it, twists it, knots it and says to his fellows « *We shall call this usy / gesture a **ned** !* »

7000 years after Fred, the whole world speaks of **networking**.

Ben, the basket maker, braids wicker and says to his fellows « *We shall call this usy / gesture a **plek** !* »

7000 years after Ben, the whole world talks about plexus, complex, duplex and multiplex.

Will weaves flax fiber and says to his fellows « *We shall call this usy / gesture a **web** !* »

7000 years after Will, the whole world talks about the web - and it's not a spider web as some authors wrote !!!

Note that if I write « *The complex network of the web.* » I say « *The braid knotted web.*»

All the way through my research work, I pay attention how the metaphors are built.

To create a metaphor is using a word created by an ancient time artisan to talk of a more sophisticated thing :

- the body - plexus
- the ideas - a complex model
- the new technologies - a multiplexer for the web

Not only the artisans but other inventors in the « tribe » create metaphors. `

Julian Jaynes studies the vocabulary of the Iliad.

He observes that the Greeks of this time describe « thoughts » « soul » by using names of physical organs.

3000 years after

We still use the « organs words » of the Greeks in words like :

- cyclothymia - from the thymus
- schizophrenic - phrenes = kidneys
- to be a « heart-full » person, cordiality.
- etc.

Everything is complex but ...

... what is important is the choice made by the seeker to study his research object as complex.

This choice is at the opposite of what is called the analytical method where complex things are parted into their components.

An analytical study of the bicycle

Knowing the parts says nothing about the the operation of the whole.

It's true for the machine, for the body, for thinking processes, for the world ecology, for the Internet, etc.

As my research work was on « the ecology of thinking bodies in front of machines for the Internet » I needed to consider my research object as complex.

Hence the need for a multi-referential method.

A constructivist perspective

I suggest we imagine the dialogue :

Me : « *I'm working on a paper about the importance of bacteria for Miguel de Cervantes and Don Quixote.* »

You : « *What are you inventing ???* »

Me : « *Inventing ? No. Remember the famous story of the fresh cheese left in Quixote's helmet and he puts the helmet on his head and the whey begins to trickle down on his front and in his eyes.* » (1)

You : « *So what ?* »

Me : « *To produce cheese, bacteria are needed.* »

You : « *Sure.* »

Me : « *For some of the beers.* »

You : « *Ah ?* »

Me : « *For the smell in the forest and the smell from warriors bodies.* »

You : « *Yes !* »

Me : « *For mud/clay houses.* »

You : « *Really ?* »

Me : « *This was just to show you what is constructivism.* »

At first glance, a novel is not about bacteria ! But you may construct ...

The fighting of the windmills by Quixote as a « good example » of a research object

Quixote on the way to fight the windmill

We keep the examples of our constructivism simple.

The windmills of the Mancha region are not interesting in their « objective reality » but in how :

- Cervantes deals with the windmills
- Quixote deals with the windmills
- Sancho deals with the windmills
- We deal with the windmills for the sake of a research method didactics

I take this example - Quixote fighting the windmills - because it contains :

- human beings
- relationships between these human beings
- usies = windmills
- relationships between a human and a usy
- weather conditions affecting the usy and the human
- etc.
-

Humans, windmills and weather conditions are the 3 dimensions of my research.

As we have seen, the dimensions of the research are not given in advance : we may research on bacterias or trees or the process of love in the work of Cervantes.

Extracting dimensions of the object and representing them

With the Sketchup software I draw a 3D space bordered by 3 symbolic limits : grass, sky and a wall.

In this 3D space, I install the three dimensions I choose to study :

1. The characters : Quixote & Sancho mainly
2. A usy : a windmill
3. Sun & wind

Extracting 3 dimensions from Cervantes story

Inventing a dimension

We have seen that it is « as if » the theme of bacterias was invented and not discovered. The theme of « sun » has this same « as if it was invented ».

I have browsed the adventures of Quixote seeking for the word « sun ». (2)

The result is incredible.

In each chapter there is about one reference to the sun.

And it is never a reference « like that » but as if the sun was a character of the novel.

There are references to the Greek mythology of the sun. Chapter 41

The Sun-Phoebus is declared as a benevolent God to be worshiped by the author. Chapter 45.

Sancho « swears to the sun ». Chapter 47

« It seems that the sun came up to shed light on the sacrifice. » Chapter 72

« The sun gives light to the way to the other life. » Chapter 55

This looks like a shamanic travel to the otherworld.

When looking to these sentences, it looks like a sort of paganism.

Then other sentences link the errant knight with the reality and the symbol of the sun.

« Resisting hard life under the sun » is a qualifier of the true errant knight Chapters 6 & 17

« Highwaymen and thugs fight in the dark, knights fight with sun as a witness » Chapter 14

« The life of the knight begins with the sunset. » Chapters 43, 61 & 68

« Some people try to « get the moon » but errant knights try to « get the sun » Chapter 38

« Women are like a sun or wear sun representations » Chapters 7, 10, 32 & 48

So the theme of the sun was there before - under the author's pen.

But as an identified dimension for a research work it is as if it was invented.

When the wind gives life to the windmill-giant

The second dimension we choose is the one of usies.

The usy « windmill » has a special status - see the full story (3)

For Sancho it is just a windmill.

For the hallucinating Quixote, a windmill is a giant he must fight.

The knight attacks at Rocinante's full gallop.

At the very moment his lance touches the windmill sail, the wind blows and Quixote and Rocinante roll onto the ground.

This is a useful metaphor to understand Quixote's madness.

And this represents also Cervantes' madness who joins an army, loses an arm and is a prisoner of the the Barbary pirates of Algiers for 5 years.

We described how the character of Sancho comes from the discovery of Nasreddin Hoca in the jails. Bois 2002

What is a referential text ?

Michel Foucault - The Order of Things - says that, in human sciences, a text has a power for elucidation.

Psychoanalysis referential texts can shed light on the characters

Saying that, Foucault is « against » the idea that a human science seeker has the power for explaining i.e. make a firm link between a cause and an effect.

Human science is not physical science !

If we take our exercise on the dimension « sun » we may say that we have the modest objective to elucidate, to put light on a characteristic of Cervantes' work.

We don't seek to prove anything.

Our observations about the presence of the sun lead us to « feel » this kind of paganism in the story of Quixote.

In 1616, both Cervantes and Shakespeare leave the scene of life.
During their career as authors they had a similar problem.
Both tell for the King or the Queen a story respectful of the official religion AND show that life and human thought is richer than the codified religious system.
When I write this sentence the referential texts are in René Girard's work.
He analyses some dimensions of Quixote in *Deceit, Desire and the Novel: Self and Other in Literary Structure*.
And the literary tricks of Shakespeare in *A theater for envy*.

René Girard's referential texts shed light on the sun as a pagan item for Cervantes
The same modest ambition goes for the third dimension.

Books of mediology can shed light on the role and meaning of the windmill

Each dimension can be « enlightened » by 2 or more authors.

Some author's model are interesting because they work « through » the dimensions or over.

Peter Sloterdijk's sphere referential can shed light over the whole system

Islets of knowledge

We have seen the two phases :

- identify and select a dimension of the research object
- use a referential text as a tool for working on a dimension

The result is a text (+ visual elements) that we call an « islet of knowledge ».

Three islets of knowledge in the ocean of knowledge and ignorance

From geography to heptagraphy

From the advent of Wikipedia's paradigm onward, knowledge is more organized in « modules » than ever.

WikiPedia articles and sub articles, academic publications, MOOCS' parts, etc. are different sizes of modules of knowledge.

For example, the corpus of geography is made of knowledge modules.

Geo-graphy as a set of modules of knowledge

There is also hydrography & nosography.

More generally, a « graphy » is a set of modules of knowledge.

The other disciplines are said to be « logies » - psychology, sociology, anthropology, etc.

A multi-referential seeker is not qualified in full disciplines - logies.

His modest capacity is to use a small part of a discipline - a referential text - to shed light on a dimension of a system.

In the case of a PhD dissertation, a « graphy » is a set of islets of knowledge.

Here we have the set of knowledge islets about online gamers in the dimension of new technologies.

The gamers are installed in the web.

We have seen the set of metaphors web / network / complexus of usies.

The complete using process involves hardware and software - from the headset to the satellite.

The production of text/knowledge on that, we call it plexography.

An item for mediography :
the roll / volumen

**The PhD dissertation is made of 7 graphies
so we call it a multi-referential heptagraphy**

1. EPISTEMOGRAPHY

How online knowledge garners appear in a time / episteme / paradigm

2. PLEXOGRAPHY

As we have seen, it is about web, network and complexus of usies

3. SEMIOGRAPHY

Is about signs and languages.

For example the availability of a lot of graphic possibilities signals the end of the « mostly textual » publications.

4. MADIOGRAPHY

Mediology is the science of « transport » in the most general meaning.

Especially transport for cultural transmission.

In our Phd we have studied the transport of texts and ideas with usies - from the roll to the iPhone.

5. SYSTEMOGRAPHY

It is the study of the systems in which the online knowledge garners are present - education, daily needs and curiosity, etc.

6. TECHNOGRAPHY

Is the study of the technical dimensions.

7. TOPOÏGRAPHY

Refers to the « topoï » / spheres model proposed by Peter Sloterdijk - picture p. 16.

Invention, discovery and creativity under constraint

Back to Cervantes and Quixote.

We have followed the seeker's milestones on his way :

MILESTONE 1

The « crude » text by Cervantes.

M2

Choosing to study 3 dimensions = humans, usies and the sun.

M3

Seeking for predecessors who have developed referential texts able to shed light on the dimensions.

M4

Organizing the referential texts within graphies projects.

M5

Writing and drawing knowledge islets within graphies.

M6

Installing the islets and graphies into the global picture of the episteme / paradigm.

M7

Imagine the future

When a constraint is given to an author by a third party or by himself it is generally observed that this constraint increases the potential of invention, discovery and creativity.

This is what happened to me during 7 years - 4 dissertations.

Hence I want to share this experience with fellow seekers.

One will follow the paved path.

Another, on the contrary, will invent his own path inspired by my adventures with Quixote and the online knowledge garners.

Notes

(1) « And turning to Sancho, he asked for his helmet, and since Sancho hadn't had time to take the cottage cheese out, he had to hand it over as it was. Don Quixote took it, without noticing what was in it, and quickly put it onto this head. Since the cottage cheese was squeezed, the whey began to trickle down all over don Quixote's face and beard, which startled him so much that he said to Sancho: "What can this be, Sancho? You'd think my brain was softening ... » Chapter 17

(2) Sun has a notable place in Quixote's life :

« But we true knights errant—**in the sun**, in the cold, in the inclemencies of the skies, by night or by day, on foot or on horseback—measure the earth with our own feet ... verify that **the sun affects** both combatants equally Chapter 6

« "But in truth, señor," responded Sancho, "when I saw this sun of Dulcinea del Toboso ... » Chapter 7

« Don't you see that they're these three women, as resplendent **as the sun itself** at midday? » Chapter 10

« But since it isn't a good idea to take up arms in the dark, like highwaymen and thugs, let's wait for the day to arrive so **the sun can witness** our combat. » Chapter 14

« But let the knight errant scour the corners of the earth, penetrate into the most intricate labyrinths, attack impossible things every step of the way, resist the **burning rays of the desert sun** in the middle of summer ... » Chapter 17

« Maese Pedro didn't want to have any more disputes with don Quixote, whom he knew very well, and so he got up **early before the sun** came up, and, taking the remnants of his puppets and his ape, also went away in search of adventures. » Chapter 26

« And they do me the most harm and wound me where they see I'll feel it the most, because to take his lady away from a knight errant is to take the eyes away with which he sees, the sun that gives him light, and the nutrition that sustains him. » Chapter 32

« What should I do when they promise the Phoenix of Arabia, the Crown of Aridiana, the horses of the Sun, pearls from the Southern Sea, the gold of Tíbar, the balm of Pancaya ? » Chapter 38

« Hold on, brave Sancho, for you're tottering a bit. Be careful not to fall! Your fall would be worse than the one the daring lad had who tried to drive the chariot belonging to the Sun, his father. » Chapter 41

« ... he who doesn't **wake up with the sun** doesn't enjoy the day» Chapter 43

« **Thymbraeus** here, **Phoebus** there, now archer, now doctor, father of poetry, inventor of music, you, who always come out but—though you seem to—never set! To you I say, **oh, sun!** with whose help man engenders man... To you, I say that you should favor and **illuminate the darkness of my intellect** so that I can faithfully report, point by point, the narration of what went on in the government of the great Sancho Panza, for without **you**, I feel tepid, dejected, and confused. » Chapter 45

« Well, señor doctor Pedro Recio de Mal Agüero, native of Tirteafuera, a village on the right hand side when you go from Caracuel to Almodóvar del Campo, graduate of **Osuna**, get out of here. If not, **I swear to the sun** that I'll get a bludgeon and,

starting with you, clobber all doctors on this insula, at least those that I feel are ignorant. » Chapter 47

« ... see the beauty of my mistress the duchess—that complexion of her face resembles a shiny polished sword blade, those two cheeks of milk and scarlet that have **the sun on one side** and the moon on the other, ... » Chapter 48

« at the end of which he saw a blurred light which seemed to be from the sun that came in from somewhere, and this seemed to indicate that what he had thought to be the road to the other life had an opening at the end. » Chapter 55

« The master of ceremonies placed them so that the sun favored neither one » Chapter 56

« This was such a sight that it amazed Sancho, confused don Quixote, and **caused the sun to stop in its orbit just to see them**, and all of them stood in marvelous silence. » Chapter 58

« Aurora gave way to the sun, who, with a face larger than a shield, starting at the horizon, began to rise little by little. » Chapter 61

« At this point, day came and the **rays of the sun** shone on Sancho's face, and he woke up and stretched his limbs and shook himself. **He saw** the damage done to his supplies by the pigs ... » Chapter 68

« And it must be that the enchanters who pursue don Quixote the Good, have tried to pursue me using don Quixote the Bad. But I don't know what to say. I swear I left him in the Asylum of the Nuncio of Toledo for treatment, and here's another don Quixote, although quite different from mine. ... It seems that **the sun came** up to shed light on the **sacrifice ...** » Chapter 72

(3) « “Look, your grace,” responded Sancho, “what you see over there aren't giants—they're windmills; and what seems to be arms are the sails that rotate the millstone when they're turned by the wind.”

“It seems to me,” responded don Quixote, “that you aren't well-versed in adventures—they are giants; and if you're afraid, get away from here and start praying while I go into fierce and unequal battle with them.”

And saying this, he spurred his horse Rocinante without heeding what his squire Sancho was shouting to him, that he was attacking windmills and not giants. But he was so certain they were giants that he paid no attention to his squire Sancho's shouts, nor did he see what they were, even though he was very close. Rather, he went on shouting: “Do not flee, cowards and vile creatures, for it's just one knight attacking you!”

At this point, the wind increased a bit and the large sails began to move, which don Quixote observed and said: “Even though you wave more arms than Briaræus, you'll have to answer to me.”

When he said this—and commending himself with all his heart to his lady Dulcinea, asking her to aid him in that peril, well-covered by his shield, with his lance on the lance rest—he attacked at Rocinante's full gallop and assailed the first windmill he came to. He gave a thrust into the sail with his lance just as a rush of air accelerated it with such fury that it broke the lance to bits, taking the horse and knight with it, and tossed him rolling onto the ground, very battered. »

Source : [Texas A&M university Cervantes project](#)

(4) An important step for the spread of the Internet protocol for communication between computers - TCP-IP - happened in June 1989, when the [University of California, Berkeley](#) has put the code developed for [BSD UNIX](#) - the computer operating system - into the public domain.

[Tim Berners-Lee](#) published the first web site, which described the project itself, on 20 December 1990; it was available to the Internet from the CERN network.

The IMAP protocol for webmail was defined in 1988.

(5) [Jacques Ardoino](#) on French Wikipedia

References

Christian Bois

1. [List of 20 of my publications in Google Scholar](#) including PhD

2. I have 1239 online articles under the auspices of [Une fabrique de communs](#)
[A selection](#)

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